

REASONS FOR THE EMERGENCE OF INTERLINGUISTIC PHRASEOLOGICAL COMMONALITY

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15173108>

ANNOTATION

This article presents the reasons for the emergence of interlingual phraseological community and the views of linguists in replenishing the phraseological fund of the language, as well as the ways of the emergence of English phraseological borrowings into the Russian language. The extralinguistic reason for the emergence and existence of interlingual phraseological correspondences are interlingual phraseological coincidences or parallels.

Keywords: Extralinguistic, linguistic, borrowing, typological basis, folklore, international elements, interpretation.

INTRODUCTION

The reasons for interlingual phraseological commonality can be explained only by taking into account the sources of origin of phraseological units. Scientists who study the issues of origin are unanimous in the fact that most phraseological units arise on national soil. It is precisely such phraseological units that, as a rule, constitute the most original, unique part of any national language. The main sources of enrichment of phraseology are living colloquial speech, folklore, national fiction and journalism.[1]

At the same time, as linguists note, phraseological borrowings play an important role in replenishing the phraseological fund of any language. Language contacts between the peoples of many countries at various levels, close contacts between people contribute to the process of interlingual lexical and phraseological borrowings, which in turn leads to the emergence of a common interlingual lexical and phraseological fund.

Thus, the emergence of interlingual phraseological correspondences can be explained primarily by linguistic reasons. These include:

1. Mutual phraseological borrowings between contacting languages, for example, phraseological borrowings of Russian from English and English from Russian, as well as Russian from Uzbek and Uzbek from Russian;
2. Borrowing of identical phraseological units by comparable languages from common linguistic sources.

The extralinguistic reason for the emergence and existence of interlingual phraseological correspondences are interlingual phraseological coincidences or parallels, that is, cases when phraseological correspondences arise in different

languages independently of each other due to the common culture, logical and figurative-associative thinking of different peoples.

From the above it follows that for interlingual phraseological correspondences, phraseological borrowings serve as a genetic base, and independent interlingual phraseological coincidences serve as a typological base. В задачи этого раздела входит следующее:

1. To identify English phraseological borrowings in the Russian language as the genetic basis of English-Russian phraseological correspondence; to determine the proportion of English phraseological borrowings in comparison with the proportion of phraseological borrowings in the Russian language from other languages, in particular, from French and German;

2. To examine the issue of the presence of Russian phraseological units in the English language as a real or potential genetic base for English-Russian phraseological correspondence; to outline the paths, methods and sources for searching for Russian phraseological borrowings in the English language;

3. To identify identical phraseological borrowings by Russian and English from common linguistic sources as the genetic base of English-Russian phraseological correspondence;

4. To outline the ways and sources of interlingual (in this case Russian-English-Uzbek) phraseological coincidences as a typological basis of interlingual phraseological correspondences.

It should be noted that the solution of the set tasks requires addressing the etymology of phraseological units – correlates of English-Russian phraseological correspondence. It presupposes, first of all, establishing the sources of origin of these units and explaining the genetic connections that exist between borrowed phraseological units and their prototypes. In order to determine the etymological source of a phraseological unit, it is necessary to establish a more or less precise time of the emergence of this unit, which in most cases is not possible.

Works devoted to political, economic, cultural ties, literary relations between Russia and Great Britain show the presence of favorable historical ground for lexical and phraseological borrowings from English into the Russian language.. English phraseological borrowings penetrated into the Russian language mainly through written means, through translations of the works of outstanding English writers into Russian. In addition to translations of works of fiction, the mass media – the press, radio, television – also contribute to the process of mutual influence of the English and Russian languages, as well as the penetration of international elements into them (including phraseological units).

CONCLUSION

At the same time, there are still many unresolved issues in this area. Thus, the full corpus of English phraseological borrowings in the Russian language has not been determined. There are few theoretical works that consider the causes, ways and means of penetration of English phraseological units into the Russian language.[2] It has not been established for which phraseological borrowings in the Russian language the

English language served as an etymological source, and for which – as a historical source, that is, genetic connections between the phraseology of the Russian and English languages have not been identified. The problems mentioned can serve as the subject of more than one study.

Thus, in total, about 400 ERUPhC were identified that arose as a result of phraseological borrowings by English, Russian and Uzbek languages from common sources. It was the comparative study of phraseological units of unrelated languages that made it possible to identify the most significant and profound similarities and differences between the phraseological systems of two or more languages, and also to determine how they manifest themselves in the general aspects of languages - functional-semantic, formal-semantic and structural. Another advantage of the comparative study of the phraseological fund of different languages is that it allowed us to discover intralinguistic and extralinguistic factors of their functioning in the language. It is advisable to study phraseological units not only within the framework of the dictionary interpretation of their meaning, but also their use in a literary text.

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